

Permission-less and Distributed Framework for Traffic Sensing by the Crowd

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Abstract—Mobile crowd sensing is a large-scale sensing paradigm based on the power of user-companioned devices, which allows mobile users to share local knowledge acquired by their sensor-enhanced devices. The aggregation of this information provides large-scale sensing and community intelligence mining, replacing static sensing infrastructures. A centralized aggregation brings unavailability and censorship issues to community-driven services. We propose a framework for decentralized and open mobile crowd sensing based on the blockchain protocol.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in the effective integration of networked information systems, sensing and communication devices, data sources, decision making, and physical infrastructure are creating new opportunities to reduce traffic congestion, fight crime, foster economic development, reduce greenhouse gases, and make local governments more open, responsive, and efficient. There has been a worldwide trend toward smart cities, which are beginning to harness the power of sensors, engage citizens equipped with smartphones, cloud computing, high-speed networks, and data analytics.

Successful society and city management relies on efficient monitoring of urban and community dynamics for decision and policy making. To achieve this, traditional sensing techniques (*e.g.*, sensor networks) usually leverage distributed sensors to acquire real-world conditions. However, though there has been a growing body of studies on sensor networks, commercial sensor network techniques have never been successfully deployed in the real world for several reasons, such as high installation cost, insufficient spatial coverage, or lack of scalability.

Mobile crowd sensing (MCS) is a large-scale sensing paradigm based on the power of user-companioned devices, including mobile phones, wearable devices, and smart vehicles... MCS allows the increasing number of mobile phone users to share local knowledge (*e.g.*, local information, ambient context, noise level, and traffic conditions) acquired by their sensor-enhanced devices, and the information can be further aggregated in the cloud for large-scale sensing and community intelligence mining. The mobility of large-scale mobile users makes MCS a versatile platform that can often replace static sensing infrastructures. A broad range of applications are thus enabled, including traffic planning, environment monitoring, mobile social recommendation, or even public safety.

While aggregating information in the cloud provides a scalable computing environment, it is still a centralized environment. A failure of the cloud provider would interrupt the whole service. Furthermore, the cloud provider must here be trusted, as it can censor information from the system. One way to overcome the availability problem would be to distribute the service among multiple cloud providers. However, this approach does not protect the system against censorship, as one cloud-provider can still suppress or modify information.

We propose to mitigate these issues with a framework for mobile crowd sensing based on the blockchain protocol, which allows for a distributed, asynchronous and permission-less data aggregation. Our decentralized approach is censorship-resilient, while still making use of a cloud-like infrastructure.

We choose to describe our framework for the traffic sensing scenario, where participant want to query the system for the current traffic status on a given road. This real-life problem allows us to better illustrate the encountered issues and provided solutions.

In Section II we present the blockchain protocol, along with other requirements. Section III defines the model we adopted, and Section III contains the implementation of our framework. We detail some related works in Section V. We conclude in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

We start by presenting the motivation behind the *blockchain* technology, and a high-level view of its implementation. We then give a brief description of two systems used by the blockchain protocol to deter service abuses, *proof-of-work* and *proof-of-stake*, along with the required basic principles on *digital signatures*.

A. Traffic Monitoring

The goal of traffic monitoring is to provide near real-time information on road usage, that is being able to estimate the traffic flow of a given road at a given time. The system must provide current road usage, along with meaningful statistics on past traffic information. This last point motivates our usage of the blockchain technology, as it provides a reliable historic of application data.

B. Blockchain

We are interested in sharing data on a distributed network because it offers several properties that would

go well with such a system. Besides the defining property of sharing work and power of decision among peers, the fact that such a network can be asynchronous fits our needs, because delays in communication will certainly occur in a large system where all users may not always have reliable access to the network (for example people traveling in the countryside). We would also want our system to be permissionless, ie. for users to be able to go in and out of the system at will, because that is exactly how real automobile networks behave. That is why we will base our implementation on a blockchain protocol, a type of distributed algorithm that verifies these wanted properties and was introduced by Nakamoto in 2008 [1] as the foundation of the now widely used Bitcoin currency.

The purpose of a blockchain is to allow the users of an asynchronous distributed network to share a common history on the events that impact the state of the system, in our case the presence of a traffic jam or not, even when users may join or quit the network at any moment without the need for permission. A blockchain is a protocol in which each user possess a variable *state* containing *blocks*. Blocks themselves contains a set of *messages* and a header pointing at the most recently created block before them. The blocks thus form a chronologically ordered chain, hence the name “blockchain”. We want to achieve a *public* ledger, ie. a common set of blocks that verifies the properties of persistency (once a message gets added to the ledger, it is never removed) and liveliness (if enough honest players want a message to be added to the ledger, it will eventually be added). Such a ledger should be strongly resistant to common attacks such as sybil (when an attacker spawns lots of new players, in this case to control the messages added to the ledger) and allow each user to trust the data it contains. In 2016, Pass [2] proved that a blockchain that possesses the properties of *consistency* (the fact that all users share an identical chain of a growing number of blocks), *future self-consistence* (the fact that this common chain does not change as time goes on), *chain-growth* (the fact an honest player’s chain will grow with as time goes on) and *chain quality* (the fact that honest players actually get their messages added into the the chain) will allow for such a ledger.

Path also proved that the Nakamoto protocol [1] indeed possessed these properties. In this protocol, there are three types of nodes in the network: *players*, who create messages and broadcasts them to the network; *miners* who build blocks by collecting the messages they receive (once a block is mined, this block is broadcast within the network); *users* who add the blocks they receive into the blockchain if and only if all the messages they contain are valid.

To ensure that at least one block is already shared by at least all the users and miners, the first block of the chain, called genesis block, which purpose is solely to be said first block, is directly encoded into the protocol, so that every node that uses it will automatically accept the genesis block. As for subsequent blocks, it is definitely possible

Figure 1. blockchain example (with a fork)

for two different blocks to be accepted by two different users, thus creating a fork that *de facto* transforms the chain into a tree.

In order to preserve the unicity of the ledger shared by all users, a branch must be chosen and one user must accept the other block and discard his own. To solve this problem, a user will, upon receiving a block, check if it represents a chain longer than the one represented by his last accepted block. If so, he will discard this block and accept the new one. If not, he will discard the new block. In the former case, if there exists messages that are present in the discarded block but not in the newly accepted chain, he will broadcast them to the system for the miners to add them into the block they will start working on. This method allows for the consistency property to be respected. Now, one last issue is the need for users to add their block into the blockchain in a desynchronised fashion. Otherwise the forks created by the addition of blocks from different users would never be solved. This is the goal of the proof-of-work scheme.

C. Proof-of-work

A proof-of-work [3], [4] (POW) is a computational puzzle used to deter denial of service attacks [5] and other service abuse by requiring some work from the service requester. It is a piece of data which is expensive (costly, time-consuming) to produce but efficiently verifiable by others and which satisfies certain requirements. It was first introduced as cost-functions in [3].

Common proof-of-work implementations use a hash function as a building block, as cryptographic hashes are hard to invert. This is the case of Hashcash [6], used as the Bitcoin [1] mining function, which is using a double SHA256 function.

The proof-of-work relies on energy use, since it requires high computation power. Alternatives to POW have been proposed to mitigate this issue, such as the proof-of-stake (POS). The main idea behind POS is that instead of using its capital to buy computers and electricity to compute POW tokens, a user use its capital to acquire the tokens. In cryptocurrencies such as Peercoin [7], a proof-of-stake asks users to prove ownership of a certain amount of currency (their “stake” in the currency).

D. Proof-of-stake

The main consideration regarding the PoW is the energy required to produce hashing operation [8]. At the time of this writing 2^{51} hash are generated by the network to create a single block. Many discussions on the bitcoin forum

led to a mechanism based on “proof-of-stake” (PoS) [9] to obtain a more energy efficient process. Instead of using computational resources, the miners randomly elect one of them based on the amount of stake reported in the ledger that each of them possesses. This protocol creates a self-referential blockchain relying on the stakeholders to assign work to themselves and has been formally studied by Bentov [10]. This process does not require computational power from the miners, but do suffer from some security issues [10].

E. Digital Signature

A digital signature is a mathematical scheme employing asymmetric cryptography for demonstrating the authenticity of digital messages. Although digital signatures are not the focus of this paper, it is deeply used by the blockchain protocol. We only provide a brief overview; the interested reader is referred to [11]. A digital signature scheme consists of three algorithms:

- A key *generation* algorithm that selects a private key uniformly at random from a set of possible private keys. The algorithm outputs the private key and a corresponding public key.
- A *signing* algorithm that, given a message and a private key, produces a signature.
- A signature *verifying* algorithm that, given the message, public key and signature, either accepts or rejects the message’s claim to authenticity.

III. MODEL

In this section we define the model under which our framework operates. We describe the entities involved, the infrastructure assumptions, and the security model that is managed.

A. Entities

There are four entities interacting in our framework.

Sensors are mobile nodes who want to transmit their local observations to the system. They correspond to the cars in our framework.

Aggregators are geographically distributed to aggregate local observations of sensors nodes. They possess limited calculation power and memory capabilities.

Miners provide computing power. They are always accessible. Filling stations play the role of miners.

The **clients** want to read the aggregated data of the system.

B. Infrastructure

We make the assumption that sensors nodes always know their geographic position, *ie.* they have access to a GPS signal at all time, without any sort of spoofing. Furthermore, we assume a nearly full network coverage for the sensor. While we allow for some of the messages sent by the sensors to the aggregators to be lost, this must be in adequation with the distribution of honest vs malicious sensors.

C. Security

We assume that all entities are correct, *ie.* they follow the protocol. Sensors can however lie about the reported state, maliciously or due to a hardware or software error. We require a strict majority ($> 50\%$) of honest sensors. Aggregators are trusted entities. Miners can ignore transactions. We allow for miners collusion but we assume that colliding nodes are known. We say that miners collusion occurs when two filling stations belong to the same corporation. We assume there exists a directory of aggregators and miners nodes, along with a database of digital signatures used by these nodes. This directory allows a sensor to identify its nearest aggregators nodes. The privacy of observers is not addressed in this paper.

IV. FRAMEWORK

In this section we detail our framework, which is depicted in Figure 2. Embedded sensors on cars (1) collect observations on the local traffic state, which are (2) sent to local nodes. These nodes (3) pre-process and aggregate data, before (4) sending it to a miner. The miner (5) aggregates the collected reports into a ‘block’, before (6) broadcasting the result.

The rest of this section gives the formal structure of our central data structure—a blockchain—before describing the algorithms run by each entity.

Figure 2. Global view of the framework

A. Blockchain Structure

Definition 1 (Transaction). A transaction t is a tuple such that

$$t = (\sigma_a, pk_s, a)$$

with σ_a the signature over a with the private key pk_s of a sensor s , pk_s the public key of the sensor s and a an aggregate modelled as a couple

$$a = (r, st)$$

with r a road and st its status.

Definition 2 (Block). A block b_i is build by a miner m and is defined by

$$b_i = (\sigma_h, pk_m, h)$$

with σ_h the signature over h with the private key of m , pk_m the public key of the miner m and h the header which is modeled as

$$h = (\text{Hash}(b_{i-1}), T, \text{time})$$

with $\text{Hash}(b_{i-1})$ the result of the relation Hash over the previous block b_{i-1} , T a set of transactions and time the timestamp when the block b_i has been created by the miner m .

In our context, the miners do not own stake but a public key registered in a decentralized database. The PoS mechanism we use in our framework is based on the idea of a block containing the necessary information for the miners to know who has to create the next block. The timestamp written in the header of the block is used as the seed of a, globally shared over the miners, random number uniformly generating function which draw the public key of the newly elected miner.

A single entity in our system which owns a significant percentage of the miners can create a sequence of multiple blocks with high probability. To prevent the censorship that can be created by this collusion of miners, a more robust method can be use to elect the next miner. The owner of the filling stations are detailed in the database, which gives the opportunity to draw uniformly into the set of miners not owned by the previous miner's owner.

Definition 3 (Proof-of-stake). *PoS is a relation defined as*

$$\text{PoS} \rightarrow t \times pk_{b_i} \rightarrow PK \setminus PK_{b_i}$$

such that from a timestamp t and the public key of the previous miner pk_{b_i} draws uniformly over the set of miner's public key minus the set of miners public keys owned by the owner of the previously elected miner.

B. Sensors

Definition 4 (Traffic state). *A traffic state st is an integer which takes value into an arbitrary range depending on the required accuracy of the system. The following use of traffic states will take values into $\llbracket 0, 5 \rrbracket$, to quantify the fluidity of the traffic.*

An observation o is modeled as

$$o = (c, s, n, p)$$

with c the coordinates of the sensor, s the status of the road, n a randomly generated number and p a proof over the tuple (c, s, n) .

A car behave as a sensor in our system, a sensor which report road status. A sensor can acknowledge its position with a GPS tracking unit and evaluate the traffic status. We assume a trusted GPS tracking unit, so that the car position cannot be falsified. Whenever a car enters a road it has the ability to observe its fluidity and warn the system. Algorithm 1 describe the procedure to generate such observation.

Algorithm 1: Sensor's procedure

- 1 Let c be the car geographic position obtained from GPS.
 - 2 Let s be the current observed road state.
 - 3 Compute the proof-of-work $(p, r) \leftarrow \text{POW}(c, s)$
 - 4 Build the observation $o \leftarrow (c, s, r, p)$.
 - 5 Send observation o to the nearest aggregators.
-

A PoW is required from a sensor to generate a valid observation. The PoW is made over a target t which contains the coordinates of the car along with the observed status. We assure unicity over observations by adding a randomly generated number to t .

Algorithm 2: Sensor's POW scheme

Input : car coordinates $c \in \mathbb{R}^2$, road state $s \in \{0, 1\}$

Output: proof-of-work $p \in \mathbb{N}$

- 1 Let $n \in \{0, 2^{64}\}$ be a random integer.
 - 2 Let $p \leftarrow (c, s, n)$ of the payload.
 - 3 Let $H_p \leftarrow \text{Hash}(p)$ be the hash of our payload.
 - 4 Let $d \in \{10^1, 10^{10}\}$ be the difficulty.
 - 5 Let $t \leftarrow 2^{64} \div d$ be the target.
 - 6 Let $N \leftarrow 0$ be our nonce.
 - 7 Let g be our guess.
 - 8 **do**
 - 9 | $N \leftarrow N + 1$
 - 10 | $g \leftarrow \text{Hash}(\text{Hash}(N + H_p))$
 - 11 **while** $g > t$;
 - 12 **return** $\text{Append}(g, r)$
-

The difficulty of the proof depends on the mean time to traverse the road the car is currently reporting about. The PoW removes the ability to overflow the system to the sensors and this criteria importance will be described later as well as the fact that a sensor can still generate false information.

C. Aggregators

An aggregator's role is to remove the most of the load over the network by aggregating the observations made by the sensors. The aggregators are collecting the observations made by the sensors from at least one road. Two aggregators do not collect observations from the same road. An aggregate is generated as soon as a required amount θ_r of observations have been received for the road r . The status reported in the transaction of the aggregate is computed by an arbitrary aggregation function (e.g. Max, Mean, ...). When the transaction is finally created it is then sent to the miner in charge of mining the next block.

In our context, the majority voting aggregation function is used over the received observations for a single road. The majority voting process is negating the incoming false

Algorithm 3: The aggregator’s procedure executed upon receiving an observation from an observer.

```

1 begin
2   Let  $D$  a table associating for a road  $r$  and a status  $s$  a set of integers. Let  $pk_s$  the public key of the sensor.
3   Let  $sk_s$  the secret key of the sensor.
4 upon receiving observation  $(c, s, n, p)$  from an observer
5   begin verify
6     Let  $o \leftarrow (c, s, n)$ .
7      $\text{Assert}(\text{Hash}(o)) = p$ 
8   begin update
9     Let  $r$  be the road index associated to the position  $c$ .
10    Add  $n$  to the road’s status table  $D[r, s]$ .
11    if  $|D[r]| > \theta_r$  then /* ie. enough observation */
12      Let  $st \leftarrow \text{MajorityVoting}(D[r])$  the result of majority voting.
13       $a \leftarrow (r, st)$ 
14       $\sigma \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sk_s, a)$ 
15       $t \leftarrow (\sigma_a, pk_s, a)$ 
16      Send transaction  $t$  to  $m$  the elected miner.
17       $D[r] \leftarrow \emptyset$ 

```

Figure 3. Example of Aggregator setting

information, knowing that only the minority of the sensors can adopt an adversarial behavior

Each PoW from the received observations needs to be verified by the aggregators. The randomly generated number prevents the aggregators to add twice a single observation.

Aggregators remove the PoW from the observation to lower down the load over the network. So in order to keep the certification over the reported status, the aggregators need to sign the aggregates.

D. Miners

When a miner is elected by the PoS procedure at the commit of a block, he then has to save every valid transactions created by the aggregators. After an arbitrary amount of time W , the miner creates the block with all the saved transactions. By creating the block, the current miner chooses at random the next miner who needs to generate the block to follow. The block is then broadcasted onto the network to the other miners and clients of the system.

The miners can adopt an adversarial behavior in the system and are able to ignore unwanted transactions but are not capable of altering a certified transaction. The PoS method previously presented prevents a filling station from

Algorithm 4: The miner’s procedure executed upon receiving an aggregate from an aggregator.

```

1 Let  $T$  be a set of transactions.
2 upon receiving a transaction  $t = (\sigma_a, pk_s, a)$  from an aggregator
3   begin verify
4     // check  $pk_s$  in database
5     // check  $a$  with  $\sigma_a$  and  $pk_s$ 
6   begin update
7      $T \leftarrow \text{Append}(T, t)$ 

```

Algorithm 5: The miner’s procedure executed to mine a block.

```

1 Let  $T$  be the set of transactions.
2 Let  $pk_m$  the public key of the miner.
3 Let  $sk_m$  the secret key of the miner.
4  $previousBlock \leftarrow \text{LatestBlock}(chain)$ 
5  $parent \leftarrow \text{Hash}(previousBlock)$ 
6  $h \leftarrow (parent, T, timestamp)$ 
7  $\sigma_h \leftarrow \text{Sign}(sk_m, h)$ 
8  $newBlock \leftarrow (\sigma_h, pk_m, h)$ 
9 return  $\text{Append}(chain, newBlock)$ 

```

creating a sequence of blocks. Hence, an ignored transaction will eventually be broadcasted with the following block and the system is then not fully aware of the totally of the observations for at most W .

V. RELATED WORK

Mobile crowd sensing has often been proposed to monitor traffic congestion levels, traffic delays, and road condition problems. The *University of California, Berkeley and Nokia Corp.'s Mobile Century and Mobile Millennium projects* [12] uses GPS to monitor velocity of traffic in San Francisco, with a focus on privacy. The *Queen's University (Canada)'s CrowdITS project* [13] is a crowd-based system that provides real-time information about congestion using GPS. Real-life applications related to ours are two web mapping services: Google Traffic [14] and Waze [15]. Both services use crowd sensing to display traffic conditions [16]. However, all these approaches use a centralized infrastructure to collect and aggregate data, which is susceptible to failure and censorship.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have described in this paper an open and decentralized framework for mobile crowd sourcing of traffic data. Our approach allows a scalable and trusted aggregation of local knowledge. We advocate that other sensing scenarios can use a similar approach to provide censorship-resilience.

Future works include validation of our work through simulation or with a real-life application, along with providing a template of our contribution for general mobile crowd sensing.

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